

Studies on lead(II)-exchanged natural zeolite and its interacted derivatives with NH₃ and H₂S before and after heating

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Structural modification of natural zeolite has been carried out by heating, cation-exchange and adsorption processes. The investigation of the exchanged and interacted derivatives by XRD, FTIR and thermal methods and composition studies by neutron activation analysis establishes the possible utility of a naturally occurring Na(I) aluminosilicate-hydrate for environmental control through cation-exchange and adsorption.

The role of zeolite molecular sieves in the field of environmental control is well known¹. The molecular zeolite sieve employed in this work is a Natrolite type natural zeolite, which is available from deposits collected as a geological specimen. The naturally occurring zeolite has been used to prepare cation-exchanged derivative with lead(II) nitrate and this derivative both before and after heating has been used for adsorbing gaseous H₂S and liquor NH₃. The aim of the present study is to test the suitability of such natural material as cation-exchangers and adsorbents for H₂S and NH₃. Adsorbates like H₂S and NH₃ which pose hazards both in the atmosphere and water need to be controlled².

Results and Discussion

The original zeolite in powdered form is white in colour and so also its Pb^{II}-derivative. Heating of both the Pb^{II}-zeolite and its interacted derivatives results in a distinct colour change to orange-yellow colour. The H₂S-interacted Pb^{II}-zeolite also shows colour change indicating the presence of PbS. The orange-yellow colour of heated residues indicates formation of PbO (litharge) which is yellow in colour.

IR studies : IR spectral data of the Pb^{II}-zeolite and its interacted derivatives consist of all the characteristic bands of the natural zeolite Natrolite along with coordinated water³. The OH stretching region shows bands at 3660–3400 cm⁻¹. The strong intensity bands at 3860–3740 cm⁻¹ in all dealuminated samples can be attributed to silanol bands (Si-OH modes)⁴. The medium intensity bands at 3755–3660 cm⁻¹ in all the dealuminated samples reflect the degree of dealumination⁵. Physically adsorbed H₂S at 1384 cm⁻¹ and NH₄⁺ ions at 1512–1390 cm⁻¹ are seen in the

spectra of the adsorbed derivatives. The H₂S-interaction results in the formation of an ash-grey sample. The presence of PbS species is indicated by a strong band at 2362 cm⁻¹. Residues after heating of interacted derivative of Pb^{II}-zeolite show strong intensity bands for H₂S and NH₃, corresponding to the adsorption capacity of zeolite which increases on heating. Pre-heated Pb^{II}-zeolite and its interacted derivatives show weak intensity of OH bands, which indicates the loss of physically adsorbed water molecules.

Thermal analysis : The Pb^{II}-zeolite shows a fast step weight-loss (5.10%) at 200–320° which is attributed to loss of physically adsorbed water and a further slow step weight-loss (3.34%) at 320–440° for high temperature water loss. A third weight loss step at 440–900° shows dehydroxylation process⁶.

NH₃ and H₂S-interacted Pb^{II}-zeolite samples show a total weight-loss slightly higher than Pb^{II}-zeolite, which shows desorption of H₂S and NH₃. The H₂S-interacted Pb^{II}-zeolite shows a total weight-loss higher than NH₃-interacted Pb^{II}-zeolite, which is due to higher molecular weight of H₂S. The weight-loss recorded for residues after heating Pb^{II}-zeolite and its adsorbed samples is negligible for the latter and only about 3.0% for the former. The DTA plots do not show any endothermic or exothermic peaks. This can lead to the assumption that negligible or no thermal process takes place for these residues and except for Pb^{II}-exchanged zeolite residue the weight-losses recorded can be due to buoyancy effects⁷.

The DTA pattern for Pb^{II}-zeolite derivative shows endothermic peaks at 300 and 470° due to low temperature

dehydration and high temperature dehydration respectively. DTA pattern for NH_3 -interacted Pb^{II} -zeolite shows endothermic peaks at 270 and 470° due to dehydration and dehydroxylation and it also shows exothermic peak at 360 and 500° due to deammoniation and oxidation. The DTA pattern for H_2S -interacted Pb^{II} -zeolite shows endothermic peak at 300 and 470° and exothermic peak at 750°, corresponding to the dehydration, desorption and oxidation of adsorbate H_2S .

X-Ray studies : The X-ray diffraction data of Pb^{II} -zeolite and its interacted derivatives lead to the conclusion that the Pb^{II} -zeolite and its interacted derivatives are crystalline and orthorhombic. The presence of aluminate tetrahedra in Pb^{II} -zeolite and its interacted derivative framework is expected to cause an expansion in the lattice. Conversely, removal of aluminium results in a contraction of unit cell⁸. The diffraction data show reduction in the number of peaks due to production of defect structure after heating. Residual Pb^{II} -zeolite and its interacted derivatives are more crystalline as compared to natural zeolite and its interacted derivatives. So the material obtained by heating has good stability and good crystallinity. This stability is due to aluminium deficiency⁹. The X-ray data of residual derivatives show a shift of diffraction peaks to higher 2θ values as compared to Pb^{II} -zeolite and its interacted derivatives, which is consistent with more siliceous framework.

Neutron activation analysis : The samples were subjected to neutron activation analysis for Na^1 . The samples were irradiated for four days in a neutron flux of 8.7×10^7 n/cm² with ²⁵²Cf source. The analysis done in duplicate shows variation in Na content in the six samples from 1.26 to 2.46% and indicates high percentage of impurities in the natural zeolite sample in the form othermetallic silicates as is probable in geological specimens.

The work clearly indicates that the zeolite and its cation-exchanged form can be useful for controlling the environment and remove toxic pollutants like NH_3 and H_2S through the process of adsorption and chemical reaction.

Experimental

Naturally occurring zeolite as a geological specimen was powdered after cleaning, washing and grinding to very fine white particles. Pb^{II} -exchanged derivative of natural zeolite was prepared by treating this powdered zeolite (20 g) with saturated aqueous solution of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (100 ml) and shaken for 10 days. The reactants were warmed in a

water-bath at 60° for maximum interaction. The supernatant liquid was then decanted and fresh portion of saturated salt solution (100 ml) was added and the mixture shaken for 10 days. The process was repeated five times for maximum interaction. After 50 days, the solid zeolite was filtered and washed before air-drying. A white Pb^{II} -exchanged derivative was obtained. One part of this sample was continuously heated over a Meker burner for 3 days in a nickel crucible to get an orange-yellow derivative. Adsorbed derivatives were prepared by the procedure described in an earlier communication¹⁰.

FTIR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrophotometer. Thermal data (TGA and DTA) were recorded using a Setaram analyser in argon atmosphere at a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹ over a temperature range 0–900°. XRD data were obtained between 2θ angles of 0 to 70° using a PW1710 BASED X-ray diffractometer. Neutron activation analysis was carried out in the Institute of Science (Mumbai).

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References

1. R. Raja and P. Ratnasamy, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1995, **100**, 93; K. J. Balkus and A. G. Gabrielov, *J. Inclu. Pheno. Mol. Reco. Chem.*, 1995, **21**, 159; M. E. Davies, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1993, **26**, 311.
2. S. E. Manahan, "Environmental Chemistry", Willard Grant Press, Massachusetts, 1975.
3. G. Gottardi and E. Galli, "Natural Zeolite, Minerals and Rocks", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1984.
4. V. Bosacek, V. Patzelova, Z. Tvaruzkova and H. Stach, *J. Catal.*, 1980, **61**, 435.
5. J. Scherzer and J. L. Bass, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **79**, 1200.
6. H. A. Benesi, *J. Catal.*, 1969, **8**, 368.
7. W. W. Wendlandt, "Thermal Analysis", 3rd. ed., 1964.
8. E. F. T. Lee and L. V. C. Rees, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1987, 1531.
9. R. W. Olsson and Z. D. Rollmann, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **16**, 651.
10. S. Bhattacharya and S. P. Banerjee, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 104.